

Determination of Solubility Product of Silver Bromide at a Number of Temperatures

A. C. JHA and B. PRASAD

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna

Manuscript received 27 October 1978, accepted 9 February 1980

Solubility product of silver bromide has been determined from 15° to 55° at 10° intervals from e.m.f. measurements of a series of cells of the type given below :

EARLIER determinations¹⁻⁵ of solubility product of silver bromide differed by more than 20% in some cases. Recently Gledhill and Malan⁶ determined the solubility product by measuring conductance. Owen and Brinkley⁷ calculated the same from E° values of Ag/Ag^+ and $\text{Ag}/\text{AgBr}, \text{Br}^-$ electrodes. At some temperatures the difference in solubility product determined by the two sets of authors comes to 10%. So it was decided to undertake this study with the help of cells. $\text{Ag} \left| \text{AgBr} \begin{array}{c} \text{KBr}(x)c \\ \text{KNO}_3(1-x)c \end{array} \right| \text{KNO}_3 c \left| \begin{array}{c} \text{AgNO}_3(x)c \\ \text{KNO}_3(1-x)c \end{array} \right| \text{AgBr} \left| \text{Ag} \right.$ These cells were similar to those studied by Owen⁸ in the determination of solubility product of silver chloride and these cells were also studied by Gledhill and Malan⁹ at 25°. Our method of calculation is slightly different from that of Owens or Gledhill and Malan.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared in molarity in doubly distilled water from G.R. quality salts at the experimental temperature. The concentrations of the stock solutions of silver nitrate and potassium bromide were checked volumetrically¹⁰. The experimental solutions were deoxygenated by passing presaturated nitrogen gas. Thermal electrolytic silver-silver bromide electrodes used in the experiments were prepared following the method of Harned and Douglas¹¹, the only difference being that the platinum spiral was coated directly with silver oxide paste instead of electroplating it first with silver and then coating with silver oxide. The electrode vessels, bridges and setting up the cells were similar to that described earlier¹². Temperature control was within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Tinsley Vernier Potentiometer was used. All the cells were studied in duplicate and the duplicates generally agreed within 0.1 mV., though in a very few cases difference went up to 0.15 mV.

The mean values of E (in absolute volts) are given in Tables 1-5. The values of 'A' in molarity scale have been taken from the work of Manov, Bates, Hamer and Acree¹³.

Discussion

At every temperature five series of experiments were performed and every series had five sets of experiments. In every series 'c' was fixed and 'x' was varied. E.M.F. of a cell of any particular series is given by

$$E = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_1}{a_2} + l.j.p. = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_1 a_3}{K_{sp}} + l.j.p. \quad \dots (1)$$

where a_1 indicates activity of silver ion in the mixture of silver nitrate and potassium nitrate, a_2 and a_3 indicate activity of silver ion and bromide ion respectively in the mixture of potassium bromide and potassium nitrate and K_{sp} indicates solubility product of silver bromide and l.j.p. the liquid junction potential. Now $a_1 = x f_+$ and $a_3 = x f_-$ where f_+ is the activity coefficient of silver ion in silver nitrate and potassium nitrate mixture and f_- that of bromide ion in potassium bromide and potassium nitrate mixture. So equation (1) reduces to

$$E = \frac{2x \cdot 2.3026RT}{F} \log(xc) = \frac{2.3026RT}{F} \log f_+ f_- - \frac{2.3026RT}{F} \log K_{sp} + l.j.p. \quad \dots (2)$$

In any series as μ is constant, f_+ and f_- will remain constant throughout. Only x will change. Now L.H.S. (represented by p) of equation (2) when plotted against x gives a straight line (Fig. 1). When

TABLE 1—TEMPERATURE 15°C.

$\mu=C$	x	E	p	q	'L'
0.0500	0.4	0.52919	0.72345		
0.0500	0.3	0.51475	0.72329		
0.0500	0.2	0.49490	0.72358	0.72350	0.73629
0.0500	0.1	0.46050	0.72360		
0.0500	0.05	0.42593	0.72345		
0.0400	0.5	0.53019	0.72445		
0.0400	0.4	0.51884	0.72418		
0.0400	0.3	0.50468	0.72430	0.72430	0.73574
0.0400	0.2	0.48433	0.72409		
0.0400	0.1	0.45022	0.72440		
0.0300	0.5	0.51657	0.72511		
0.0300	0.4	0.50557	0.72519		
0.0300	0.3	0.49147	0.72539	0.72530	0.73520
0.0300	0.2	0.47131	0.72535		
0.0300	0.1	0.43668	0.72514		
0.0200	0.6	0.50703	0.72665		
0.0200	0.5	0.49804	0.72672		
0.0200	0.4	0.48700	0.72676	0.72670	0.73478
0.0200	0.3	0.47268	0.72672		
0.0200	0.2	0.45240	0.72658		
0.0100	0.6	0.47531	0.72935		
0.0100	0.5	0.46599	0.72909		
0.0100	0.4	0.45480	0.72998	0.72840	0.73412
0.0100	0.3	0.44034	0.72880		
0.0100	0.2	0.42037	0.72897		

TABLE 2—TEMPERATURE 25°C.

$\mu=C$	x	E	p	q	'L'
0.0500	0.4	0.51665	0.71767		
0.0500	0.3	0.50191	0.71771		
0.0500	0.2	0.48105	0.71769	0.71770	0.73117
0.0500	0.1	0.44559	0.71785		
0.0500	0.05	0.40968	0.71756		
0.0400	0.5	0.51798	0.71900		
0.0400	0.4	0.50614	0.71862		
0.0400	0.3	0.49136	0.71862	0.71820	0.73025
0.0400	0.2	0.47044	0.71854		
0.0400	0.1	0.43460	0.71832		
0.0300	0.5	0.50341	0.71921		
0.0300	0.4	0.49212	0.71939		
0.0300	0.3	0.47725	0.71931	0.71920	0.72964
0.0300	0.2	0.45620	0.71908		
0.0300	0.1	0.42056	0.71906		
0.0200	0.6	0.49386	0.72113		
0.0200	0.5	0.48455	0.72119		
0.0200	0.4	0.47297	0.72108	0.72090	0.72942
0.0200	0.3	0.45799	0.72088		
0.0200	0.2	0.43735	0.72107		
0.0100	0.6	0.45988	0.72277		
0.0100	0.5	0.45050	0.72276		
0.0100	0.4	0.43891	0.72263	0.72290	0.72891
0.0100	0.3	0.42446	0.72297		
0.0100	0.2	0.40372	0.72306		

$x=0, i, j, p=0$. Hence

$$\left[E - \frac{2x \cdot 2.3026RT}{F} \log(xc) \right]_{x=0} = \frac{2.3026RT}{F} \log f_+ f_- - \frac{2.3026RT}{F} \log K_{sp} \dots (3)$$

Using the equation $-\log f_i = AZ_1^2 \sqrt{\mu} - \beta_i \mu$ and $\beta_{Ag^+} + \beta_{Br^-} = \beta$ equation (3) becomes

$$\left[E - \frac{2x \cdot 2.3026RT}{F} \log(xc) \right]_{x=0} + \frac{2x \cdot 2.3026RT}{F} A \sqrt{\mu} = \frac{2.3026RT}{F} \beta \mu - \frac{2.3026RT}{F} \log K_{sp} \dots (4)$$

Taking all the five series at any temperature, L.H.S. (represented by L) of equation (4) is plotted against

TABLE 3—TEMPERATURE 35°C.

$\mu = C$	x	E	p	q	'L'
0.0500	0.4	0.50463	0.71238		
0.0500	0.3	0.48938	0.71240		
0.0500	0.2	0.46787	0.71243	0.71250	0.72669
0.0500	0.1	0.43115	0.71251		
0.0500	0.05	0.39426	0.71244		
0.0400	0.5	0.50600	0.71375		
0.0400	0.4	0.49403	0.71363		
0.0400	0.3	0.47879	0.71367	0.71348	0.72617
0.0400	0.2	0.45728	0.71369		
0.0400	0.1	0.42030	0.71352		
0.0300	0.5	0.49155	0.71457		
0.0300	0.4	0.47976	0.71464		
0.0300	0.3	0.46421	0.71437	0.71490	0.72589
0.0300	0.2	0.44314	0.71482		
0.0300	0.1	0.40640	0.71490		
0.0200	0.6	0.48164	0.71652		
0.0200	0.5	0.47183	0.71639		
0.0200	0.4	0.46012	0.71653	0.71640	0.72537
0.0200	0.3	0.44481	0.71649		
0.0200	0.2	0.42320	0.71642		
0.0100	0.6	0.44687	0.71855		
0.0100	0.5	0.43722	0.71858		
0.0100	0.4	0.42508	0.71830	0.71840	0.72475
0.0100	0.3	0.40990	0.71840		
0.0100	0.2	0.38850	0.71853		

TABLE 4—TEMPERATURE 45°C.

0.0500	0.4	0.49416	0.70864		
0.0500	0.3	0.47831	0.70855		
0.0500	0.2	0.45623	0.70871	0.70880	0.72375
0.0500	0.1	0.41814	0.70862		
0.0500	0.05	0.38043	0.70891		
0.0400	0.5	0.49484	0.70932		
0.0400	0.4	0.48070	0.70942		
0.0400	0.3	0.46708	0.70956	0.70976	0.72313
0.0400	0.2	0.44475	0.70947		
0.0400	0.1	0.40694	0.70966		
0.0300	0.5	0.48058	0.71082		
0.0300	0.4	0.46859	0.71107		
0.0300	0.3	0.45266	0.71092	0.71125	0.72283
0.0300	0.2	0.43039	0.71087		
0.0300	0.1	0.39283	0.71131		
0.0200	0.6	0.46996	0.71244		
0.0200	0.5	0.45997	0.71245		
0.0200	0.4	0.44776	0.71248	0.71230	0.72175
0.0200	0.3	0.43175	0.71223		
0.0200	0.2	0.40943	0.71215		
0.0100	0.6	0.43428	0.71476		
0.0100	0.5	0.42438	0.71486		
0.0100	0.4	0.41216	0.71488	0.71490	0.72159
0.0100	0.3	0.39654	0.71502		
0.0100	0.2	0.37406	0.71478		

Fig. I Plot of p against x at 25°

μ , a straight line is obtained (Fig. II) and the value of $K_{sp(\text{molarity})}$ is found from the intercept. Using the expression $K_{sp(\text{molarity})} = \frac{K_{sp(\text{molality})}}{p^2}$ where p is the density of water at the temperature concerned, the value of K_{sp} on molality scale was calculated. The results are given in Table-6 along with the values of some other authors.

In the following tables (i) 'E' is the measured value of e.m.f. of the cell in absolute volts, (ii) 'p' stands for $E - \frac{2 \times 2.3026RT}{F} \times \log(xc)$, (iii) 'q' stands

TABLE 5—TEMPERATURE 45°C

$\mu=c$	x	E	p	q	'L'
0.0500	0.4	0.48360	0.70484		
0.0500	0.3	0.46780	0.70530		
0.0500	0.2	0.44478	0.70522	0.70540	0.72115
0.0500	0.1	0.40589	0.70553		
0.0500	0.05	0.36655	0.70539		
0.0400	0.5	0.48405	0.70529		
0.0400	0.4	0.47128	0.70514		
0.0400	0.3	0.45539	0.70551	0.70600	0.72009
0.0400	0.2	0.43232	6.70538		
0.0400	0.1	0.39361	0.70587		
0.0300	0.5	0.46994	0.70744		
0.0300	0.4	0.45732	0.70744		
0.0300	0.3	0.44120	0.70760	0.70743	0.71963
0.0300	0.2	0.41803	0.70735		
0.0300	0.1	0.37891	0.70743		
0.0200	0.6	0.45876	0.70888		
0.0200	0.5	0.44838	0.70882		
0.0200	0.4	0.43561	0.70867	0.70900	0.71896
0.0200	0.3	0.41943	0.70875		
0.0200	0.2	0.39678	0.70904		
0.0100	0.6	0.42180	0.71112		
0.0100	0.5	0.41163	0.71127		
0.0100	0.4	0.39908	0.71134	0.71170	0.71874
0.0100	0.3	0.38292	0.71144		
0.0100	0.2	0.36008	0.71154		

Fig. II. Plot of l against M

for extrapolated value of $E - \frac{2 \times 2.3026RT}{F} \times \log(xc)$
 when $x=0$ and (iv) 'L' stands for $q + \frac{2 \times 2.3026RT}{F}$
 $A \sqrt{\mu^-}$.

The value of E°_{Ag/Ag^+} has been recalculated from K_{sp} value of silver chloride determined by Owen⁸ and $E^\circ_{Ag/AgCl, Cl^-}$ determined by Harned and Ehlers¹⁴. With this value of E°_{Ag/Ag^+} and our value of K_{sp} of silver bromide $E^\circ_{Ag/AgBr, Br^-}$ has been calculated to be 0.0758, 0.0715, 0.0657 and 0.0595 volts at 15°, 25°, 35° and 45° respectively and the values are in fair agreement with those of standard authors¹⁶⁻²¹.

A plot of $\log K_{sp(\text{molality})}$ against $\frac{1}{T}$ gives a straight line. The value of ΔH is calculated from the slope. The value of ΔG° is calculated from the equation $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_{sp(\text{molality})}$. Now ΔH is assumed to be equal to ΔH° and ΔS° is calculated. The values given in Table-7 are nearly the same as that of Owen and Brinkley⁷ (given in brackets) which are either given in their paper or calculated from their paper.

TABLE 6—SOLUBILITY PRODUCT OF SILVER BROMIDE $\times 10^{13}$

Name of authors	15°C	25°C	35°C	45°C	55°C
Present work (a) Molarity Scale	1.479	4.948	14.237	38.340	93.867
(b) Molality Scale	1.481	4.977	14.410	39.099	96.605
Owen and Brinkley ⁷ (Molality Scale)	1.513	4.982	14.859	40.551	-
Gledhill and Malan ⁹ (e.m.f. method molality scale)	-	5.015	-	-	-
Gledhill and Malan ⁶ (Conductometric method-molality scale).	1.48 ± 0.28	5.20 ± 0.40	16.0 ± 0.5	45.6 ± 0.8	128.2 ± 1.4

TABLE—7

Temp, (°C)	ΔH° in Cals.	ΔG° in Cals.	ΔS° in e.u.
15	20112 (20542)	17030 (16899)	10.69 (12.64)
25	20112 (20150)	16898 (16780)	10.78 (11.30)
35	20112 (19749)	16809 (16679)	10.72 (9.96)
45	20112	16720	10.66
55	20112	16651	10.54

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to the U.G.C. and the Patna University for grants to one of us (A.C.J.) and to the authorities of the Patna University for the library and laboratory facilities.

References

- GOODWIN, *Z. physik. Chem.*, 1894, **13**, 645.
- THIEL, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1900, **24**, 57.
- BODLÄNDER and FITTIG, *Z. physik. Chem.*, 1902, **39**, 597.
- ABEGG and COX, *Z. physik. Chem.*, 1903, **46**, 1.
- A. E. HILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **30**, 68.
- J. A. GLEDHILL and G. MCP MALAN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, **50**, 126.
- B. B. OWEN and S. R. BRINKLEY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2233.
- B. B. OWEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2229.
- J. A. GLEDHILL and G. MCP MALAN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, **49**, 166.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis including Elementary Instrumental Analysis, Longmans, Third Edn., 1961, page 261, III. 25.
- H. S. HARNED and S. M. DOUGLAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 3095.
- S. NATH, S. ADITYA and B. PRASAD *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 683.
- G. G. MANOV, R. G. BATES, W. J. HAMER and S. F. ACREE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1765.
- H. S. HARNED and R. W. EHLERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 2179.
- H. B. HETZER, R. A. ROBINSON and R. G. BATES, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 1423.
- H. S. HARNED, A. S. KESTON and J. G. DONELSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 989.
- H. K. SINHA and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 901.
- TOWNS, GREELEY and LIETZKE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 1861.
- B. B. OWEN and L. FOERING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1575.
- H. S. HARNED and W. J. HAMER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 4496.
- H. S. HARNED and J. G. DONELSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 1280.